

A Conceptual Study on Effect of *Nagaradya Churna* in *Grahani Roga*

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ABSTRACT

Grahani Roga is one of the leading disorders of *Annavaha Srotasa*. It is mentioned in classics that root cause of all the diseases is *Mandagni*, which occurs due to improper following of dietary regimen and daily routine. The main site of *Agni* is *Grahani* the part of intestine between *Amashaya* & *Pakwashaya*. Therefore disturbance in function of *Agni* leads the disorder known as *Grahani Roga*. The symptoms of *Grahani Roga* are similar to mal-absorption syndrome, coeliac disease, tropical sprue, and irritable bowel disease as described in modern medical science. *Grahani Roga* is treated by *Shamana* and *Samsodhana Chikitsa*. *Deepana Pachana* drugs are useful to enhance the potency of *Agni*. Now the need of *Ayurvedic* medicine arises to fill this lacuna. There are number of preparation described in *Ayurveda* text and *Nagaradya Churna* in one among them and it has wonderful properties that helps in curing *Grahani Roga*. Thus *Ayurvedic* treatment is more effective in managing the patients of *Grahani Roga* by breaking the pathogenesis due to *Deepana-Pachana*, *Grahi*, and *Srotoshodhaka* properties.

KEYWORDS: *Grahani Roga*, *Agni*, *Deepana*, *Pachana*, *Grahi* etc.

INTRODUCTION

In *Ayurveda*, *Ayu* (life) is defined as conjunction of body, soul, mind and senses. Each has been given due importance in the prevention and maintenance of health and cure of disease.

In *Ayurveda* *Grahani Roga* is considered as a one among the eight *MAHAGADAS* and also one of the leading disorders of *Annavaha Srotas*. It is mentioned in classics that root cause of all the disease is *Mandagni*. Acc. to *Acharya vagbhatt* "i|| which occurs due to improper following of dietary regimen and daily routine.

Therefore, disturbance in function of *Agni* leads the disorder known as *Grahani Roga*. and whenever there is derangement in function of *Grahani Sthana* along with improper status of *Agni* that initiate the process of pathogenesis of *Grahani Roga*. "Mandagani cause improper digestion of food which moves either in *Urdhva* or *Adho marg*, when it goes in *Adho marg* then it leads to *Grahani Roga*iii.

A profound anemia & weakness may develop in last stage and this contributing to the progressive cachexia with complete loss of strength of the body. *Grahani* is the structure in the body, which is responsible for *Agnimandya*, Digestive food with help of 'Agni' the *Kayagni*. This

Agnimandya remain main factor in the disease *Grahani*.

As *Grahani Roga* is caused due to *Agnimandya*, the main line of treatment is to correct the *Agni Dushti* by administering drugs which are *Deepana* and *Pachana* in action and which corrects the intestinal motility Correction of *Agni* is a key factor in treating *Grahani Roga*. For this, *Ayurvedic* texts emphasis on the use of *Deepana* drugs that potential the *Agni* and *Pachana* drugs that enhance the digestive power of the subject.iv

"Always *Deepana Karma* all type of *Grahani Rogas* cured acc.to *Acharya Susruta*.v

Acharya susruta, *madhav*, and *vagbhatt* described *grahani roga* in classical text of *Ayurveda* and *acharya charak*, *chakradatta* described *grahani dosha* in classical text of *Ayurveda*.

Grahani Roga described in classical text of *Ayurveda* represents a group of disorders of gastrointestinal system. Malabsorption syndrome, Coeliac Sprue, Tropical Sprue, IBS, Ulcerative Colitis, Amoebiasis, Giardiasis mentioned in modern medicine may be considered under *Grahani Roga*.

Though there are few diseased conditions, which resembles like that of *Grahani Roga*, yet modern Medicine system has

“A Conceptual Study on Effect of *Nagaradya Churna* in *Grahani Roga*”

failed to find out the best drug to treat & manage the condition. Due to *Apathyakar sevan*. Changed dietary pattern many numbers of patient's of with complaining of *Grahani* are reaching doctors.

Regarding prevalence of *Grahani roga*, it is found that it affects 69% of population in india^{vi}. And Amoebiasis is the third most common cause of death from the parasitic disease. It affects 480 million people world wide, about 12% of total population. Incidence of Ulcerative colitis per lakh is found 2.2-14.3 and that of Crohn disease is 3.1-14.6.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

For this article literature review is done from *Charaka Samhita*, *Susruta Samhita*, *Astang hridaya*, *Madhav Nidan*, *Bhavprakash*, *Chakradutta*, *Ayurvedic pharmacopia* of India.

NIDANA OF GRAHANI ROGA

In Ayurveda its being considered that- *Abhojanat*, *Ajeernabhojanat*, *Attibhojanaat*, *Visamasanat*, *Asatmya Guru sheet*, *Ruksa and Sandusta Bhojanat*, *Vyadhikarshanat and Vegavidharana*.^{vii}

SAMPRAPTI OF GRAHANI ROGA

“A Conceptual Study on Effect of *Nagaradya Churna* in *Grahani Roga*”

Description of drug (*Nagaradya Churna*)

Keeping in mind that *Chikitsa Sutra* of *Grahani Roga* (If the *Ama* moves downwards and remains adhered to the *Pakvashaya* then the patient should be given purgation therapy with such drugs as are *Deepana*. If the *dosa* in its *Ama* stage is converted into *Rasa* and pervades other parts of the body the patient should undergo *Langhana* by drugs and *Vihara*. *Pachana* drugs should be given there after.) which is mentioned in *Charaka*^{viii}. almost all of the drugs are having *Deepana Pachana* and *Sangrahi* properties which all are helpful to correct the *Agni* in *Grahani*

roga. (*shunthi, ativisa, musta, dhataki, rasanjana, vatsak, bilva, patha, kutki*) Most of the drugs are *Tikta, Katu, Kashaya Rasa, Ushana Virya, Katu Vipaka* and *Tridoshaghna* in nature.^{ix} so it will be effective in *Grahani roga*. On the basis of above description, *Nagaradya Churna*. has been selected for the treatment of *Grahani Roga*. *Nagaradya Churna should be given with Anupan of Takra*. Because *Takra* is *Tridosa Shamak* and *Deepana Pachana, grahi* properties and then it should be given in *Grahani Roga*. Which is a classical reference mentioned in the *Charak Chikitsa*.^x Its content are as follows:-

DRUG	RASA	GUNA	VIRYA	VIPAKA	DOSHA KARMA
<i>Shunthi</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Laghu snigdha</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>madhura</i>	<i>Kaphavata Shamak</i>
<i>Ativisa</i>	<i>Katu, Tikta</i>	<i>Laghu, Ruksha</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Kaphapitta shamak</i>
<i>Musta</i>	<i>Tikta, katu Kashaya</i>	<i>Laghu, Ruksha</i>	<i>Shita</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Kaphapitta shamak</i>
<i>Dhataki</i>	<i>Kashaya</i>	<i>Laghu, Ruksha</i>	<i>Shita</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Kaphapitta shamak</i>
<i>Rasanjana</i>	<i>Tikta, Kashaya</i>	<i>Laghu, Ruksha</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Kaphapitta shamak,</i>
<i>Vatsak</i>	<i>Tikta, katu Kashaya</i>	<i>Laghu Ruksha</i>	<i>Shita</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Kaphapitta shamak</i>
<i>Bilva</i>	<i>Tikta, Kashaya</i>	<i>Laghu, Ruksha</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Vatakapha shamak</i>
<i>Patha</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Laghu , tikshna</i>	<i>Ushna</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>Vatakapha Shamak</i>
<i>Kutki</i>	<i>Tikta</i>	<i>Laghu , Ruksha</i>	<i>Shita</i>	<i>Katu</i>	<i>KaphaPitta shamak</i>

Most of the contents in formulation are *Tikta* (pungent), *Kashaya* (astringent) & *katu Rasa Pradhana*. *Tikta* and *Kashaya* Rasa have *Pittakapha Shamaka* properties. *Tikta* Rasa and *Kashaya* Rasa also subsides *Pittakapha* Dosha. Most of the drugs have *katu* Rasa and most of the drugs have *katu* Vipaka, which counteract the *Laghu* & *Ruksha* Guna of vitiated *Pitta* and *kapha*. Most of the drugs have *Tikta* Rasa and according to *Acharya Charaka*, and *Tikta* rasa has the ability to convert *Sama Pitta* into *Nirama pitta*, also decreases the *Pitta dravyata vridhi*, so beneficial in pacifying symptoms like *Muhurbaddham muhurdrava malapravruti, Apakva malapravruti, Dourgandhita malapravruti, Udara Shool, Udara Gourava, Vibandha, Aruchi, Alasya, Vidaha, Ajeerna*.

Shunthi, Ativisha, Musta And *Bilwa, kutki* helps in improving *Mandagni* and *Aruchi* through their *deepana- pachana karma*. *Deepana- Pachana* increases *Jatharagni* due to which there is less chance of *Avipaka* and reduces the symptoms like *Udara Gourava, Vibandha, Aruchi, Alasya, Vidaha, Ajeerna*.

Shunthi, Ativisha, Musta and *Bilwa* are also *Amapachaka* drugs which help in digesting *Ama* produced due to *Mandagni*. They also have increase the property of *Jathragni* which improves the function of *jathragni*. Thus *Rasavaha Srotodushti (Ahara Rasa)* can be treated very well.

Grahi, Purisha sangrahaniye property of *Ativisha, Musta, Dhataki, Vatsak, Bilwa* relieves *Muhurbaddham Muhurdrava Malapravruti, Apakva Malapravruti* And *Dourgandhita Malapravruti* in *Grahani Roga*.

Rasanjana and *Patha* help in relieving *Udarshool* in *Grahani Roga*.

DISCUSSION

Effect of *Nagaradya Churna* -

Dosha: Most of the drugs have *Katu, Tikta, Kashaya Rasa, Laghu- Ruksha Guna, Ushna Shita Virya, Katu Vipaka*. and *Kaphapittaghna* properties. *Kaphapitta Dosha* most aggravating factors of *Grahani Roga*.

Dushya: Most of the drugs have *Deepana- Pachana*, property which directly acts on *Agni*; thus, it leads to increase in *Jatharagni* and *Dhatvagni*. Increased *Dhatvagni* stop the process of vitiation of *Rasa Dhatu*(*Ahar Rasa*) which are the *Dushyas Of Grhani Roga*. Some of the drugs have *Grahi Sandhaniye Purishsangrahaniya, Shodhan, Ropana* properties which are essential to treat *Rasa Dushti*.

Agni and Ama: The main cause of the disease *Grahani roga* is *Mandagni*. Which leads to the production of *Ama*. *Deepana- Pachana* property of most of the drugs correct the *Mandagni* and breaks the pathogenesis of *Grahani Roga*. It also has *Amapachana* property. Hence it promotes *Jatharagni* and as a result *Jatharagni* is attained.

Srotasa: Most of the drugs possess *Laghu- Ruksha Guna* and *Tikta- katu- Kashaya Rasa* which purifies the *Srotas* through their *Srotoshuddhikara* properties.

CONCLUSION

Hence it is concluded that *Nagaradya churna* can be considered as very useful and effective Ayurvedic formulation in the management of *Grahani Roga*, as it corrects the vitiation of *Pittakapha*. Which in turns corrects the whole digestive process and results in proper functioning of *Agni*. It also helps in abolishing almost all the factors involved in pathogenesis of disease *Grahani Roga*.

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